

A NOTE ON THE STABILITY OF SOME SUBSTITUTED SEMICARBAZIDES

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Recently Baker and Gilbert (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 2777) have studied the kinetics of the transformation of hydrazine cyanate into semicarbazide and also of the conversion of semicarbazide into hydrazine cyanate. They have found that increase in ionic strength reduces the velocity of reaction in a manner which agrees with the postulate that the rate determining process is the reaction between the hydrazine and cyanate ions. It has now been considered worth while to make a comparative study of the stability of some substituted semicarbazides.

When 1-*o*-nitrophenylsemicarbazide (Guba and Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **5**, 441) is heated with aniline at 140-150°, carbanilide is obtained. Similarly, sym-di-*p*-tolylurea is obtained if *p*-toluidine is used in place of aniline. This formation of carbanilide or sym-di-*p*-tolylurea is evidently due to the interaction of aniline or *p*-toluidine with isocyanic acid (HNCO), the latter having been formed by the pyrolysis of 1-*o*-nitrophenylsemicarbazide. In this respect, 1-*o*-nitrophenylsemicarbazide resembles urea. A mixture of urea and aniline, heated at 160°, gives rise to phenylurea and carbanilide, and under this condition urea serves as an excellent source of isocyanic acid (Davis *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **44**, 2595; 1923, **45**, 1816; 1929, **51**, 1790, 1801, 1806).

The facility with which the decomposition of 1-*o*-nitrophenylsemicarbazide takes place is further demonstrated by its behaviour towards hot normal alkali, when benzoazimidol (Nietzki and Braunschweig, *Ber.*, 1894, **27**, 3381) is readily formed.

When, however, 1-phenylsemicarbazide is heated with aniline at 150-155°, 1:4-diphenylsemicarbazide is obtained and no trace of carbanilide is formed. This shows that 1-phenylsemicarbazide is much more stable than 1-*o*-nitrophenylsemicarbazide.

EXPERIMENTAL

*Action of Aniline upon 1-*o*-Nitrophenylsemicarbazide: Isolation of Carbanilide.*

1-*o*-Nitrophenylsemicarbazide (3 g.; prepared according to the method of Guba and Ghosh, *loc. cit.*) was mixed with excess of aniline in a flask (aniline acts as a solvent also) and the mixture was heated in an oil-bath at 140-150° for 3-4 hours. The mass was then treated with excess of cold dilute hydrochloric acid and shaken vigorously when a solid came out which was filtered and washed several times with dilute hydrochloric acid and water. It crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 240-241°, yield 1 g. (Found: N, 13.48. $C_{11}H_{11}ON_2$ requires N, 13.20 per cent).

The identity of this compound with a genuine sample of carbanilide was confirmed by mixed m.p.

*Action of p-Toluidine upon 1-*o*-Nitrophenylsemicarbazide: Isolation of Sym-di-*p*-tolylurea.*—The method of procedure was the same as in the case of the previous reaction. The product was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 266-268°, yield 1.2 g. from 3 g. of 1-*o*-nitrophenylsemicarbazide. (Found: N, 11.48. $C_{11}H_{11}ON_2$ requires N, 11.66 per cent). The identity of this compound with a genuine sample of sym-di-*p*-tolylurea was confirmed by mixed m.p.

*Action of Alkali upon 1-*o*-Nitrophenylsemicarbazide: Formation of Benzoazimidol*
—1-*o*-Nitrophenylsemicarbazide (2 g.) was mixed with excess of normal aqueous caustic

potash solution and the mixture heated on the water-bath for about 1 hour. The brown solution was cooled and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid, when a brown solid was precipitated which crystallised from hot water in colourless needles, m.p. 159-160°, yield 0.5 g. It gives a blood-red colouration with ferric chloride and is readily soluble in alkali. (Found : N, 31.31. C_8H_5ON , requires N, 31.11 per cent). Nietzki and Braunschweig (*loc. cit.*) recorded 157° as the m.p. of the compound.

Action of Aniline upon 1-Phenylsemicarbazide : Formation of 1 : 4-Diphenylsemicarbaside.—1-Phenylsemicarbazide (3 g.) was mixed with excess of aniline and the mixture was heated in an oil-bath at 150-155° for 3-4 hours, when ammonia was found to evolve. The mass was next treated with excess of cold dilute hydrochloric acid and shaken vigorously, when a solid was obtained, which was crystallised several times from alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 170-172° (*cf.* Skinner and Ruhemann, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1888, 58, 552). (Found : N, 18.32. $C_{12}H_{11}ON_2$, requires N, 18.50 per cent).

No trace of carbanilide was found in any of the above alcoholic extracts during crystallisation.

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